

Optical Absorption and Electron Spin Resonance Spectral Studies of Copper(II) Chalcone Complexes in different Solvents

CH. RAMAKRISHNAIAH, R. SESHADRI NAIDU and R. RAGHAVA NAIDU*

Department of Chemistry, School of Mathematical and Physical Sciences, Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati-517 502

Manuscript received 28 January 1985, revised 24 April 1986, accepted 8 May 1986

Optical absorption and electron spin resonance spectral studies on copper(II) complexes of 2'-hydroxy-, 2',2-dihydroxy-, 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy- and 2'-hydroxy-4-chlorochalcones in chloroform, dioxan, dimethyl formamide and pyridine indicate axial interaction of all these solvents with copper(II), and such interaction is greatest with pyridine. Monomeric nature of all the complexes in these solvents is indicated from magnetic moment data.

CHALCONES have been found to possess various germicidal^{1,2}, bactericidal³, fungicidal⁴ and carcinogenic⁵ activities. Methoxy- and hydroxy-chalcones can arrest the destruction of adrenaline⁶. Furthermore, naphthyl- and phenanthryl-chalcones possess potential bactericidal and carcinogenic activity⁷. The *ortho*-hydroxychalcones have good chelating properties, and were exploited as analytical reagents for the separation and determination of metal ions⁸⁻¹². The present paper describes the electronic and esr spectral studies of Cu^{II} complexes of *ortho*-hydroxychalcones, viz. 2'-hydroxychalcone, 2',2-dihydroxychalcone, 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxychalcone and 2'-hydroxy-4-chlorochalcone in different solvents, viz. chloroform, dioxan, dimethyl formamide and pyridine.

Experimental

The copper(II) complexes of 2'-hydroxy-, 2',2-dihydroxy-, 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy- and 2'-hydroxy-4-chlorochalcones were prepared according to the procedure described in the literature¹³. Spectroscopic grade chloroform, dioxan, dimethyl formamide and pyridine were used as solvents. A Shimadzu-UV-180 spectrophotometer was used to record the electronic spectra. ESR spectra were recorded at room temperature (300 K) with a Varian E-4 X-band spectrometer employing 4 to 8 gauss modulation and operating at a frequency of 9.5 GHz. DPPH has been used as the g-marker.

Results and Discussion

Cu^{II} complexes of 2'-hydroxychalcone, 2',2-dihydroxychalcone, 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxychalcone and 2'-hydroxy-4-chlorochalcone were insoluble in water and soluble in chloroform, dioxan, dimethyl formamide and pyridine. The results of elemental analysis gave 1 : 2 Cu - ligand stoichiometry.

The optical absorption spectra of all the complexes in chloroform, dioxan, dimethyl formamide and pyridine consist of intense charge transfer absorption bands in the 300-450 nm region. The electronic spectra (nujol) of the complexes gave absorption maxima in the region 19 225-24 265 cm⁻¹ and these bands were assigned to ²B_{1g} → ²E_g (d_{x²-y²} → d_{xy}, d_{yz}) transition¹⁴. In our present investigation, the band pertaining to the above transition is lowered and appeared in the region 14 493-15 152 cm⁻¹ (Table 1). Shifting of λ_{max} to longer wavelength could be attributed to the axial interaction of the solvent molecules with copper(II), the extent of which fall in the order, chloroform < dioxan < dimethyl formamide < pyridine. This observation is in agreement with the observations made by earlier investigators^{14,15}.

The room temperature esr spectra of the Cu^{II} chalcone complexes in chloroform, dioxan, dimethyl formamide and pyridine consist of four absorption lines. These four lines in the multiplet correspond to the (2I+1=4) spin orientations of the copper

TABLE 1—OPTICAL ABSORPTION DATA OF COPPER-CHALCONE COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	Compd.	λ _{max} (cm ⁻¹)				
		Chloroform	Dioxan	DMF	Pyridine	Nujol
1	Cu(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂) ₂	15 088	14 925	14 870	14 706	22 215
2	Cu(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂) ₂ · H ₂ O	14 991	14 815	—	14 498	19 225
3	Cu(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂) ₂	14 970	14 910	14 881	14 600	24 265
4	Cu(C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₂ Cl) ₂	15 152	14 870	14 815	14 706	22 215

nuclei with $I=3/2$. The esr spectra of the most copper(II) complexes in solution at room temperature normally exhibit four hyperfine lines with spin-dependent line widths due to the tumbling motion of the microcrystalline units. This tumbling motion in solution will average the anisotropic g and A values observed in solids. The values of $\langle g \rangle$ for Cu^{II} chalcone complexes increase in the order, chloroform $\langle$ dioxan $\langle$ dimethyl formamide $\langle$ pyridine (Table 2), correspond to increased axial interactions with these solvents. The $\langle A \rangle$ values of copper(II) chalcone complexes (Table 2) fall in the order, chloroform $\langle$ dioxan $\langle$ dimethyl formamide $\langle$ pyridine, indicating that the stronger the solvated

$$\langle A \rangle = P(-\alpha^2 K_0 + \langle g \rangle - 2.0023)$$

where, α^2 is the fraction of time the unpaired electron is on the copper atom, P is 0.036 cm^{-1} and K_0 is about 0.43. The α^2 values (Table 2) for the present copper complexes indicate covalent nature of the copper(II) ligand bonds. The α^2 values suggest the fall of the covalent character slightly in the order, chloroform $\langle$ dioxan $\langle$ dimethyl formamide $\langle$ pyridine. The greater interaction of pyridine with copper causes a back donation on the in-plane ligands which results in an increase in α^2 values in this solvent, compared to the other three solvents.

The values for paramagnetic susceptibility (χ_M), magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) and the Fermi contact term (K) were calculated using the expressions,

$$\chi_M = N\beta^2 \langle g^2 \rangle S(S+1)/3KT$$

$$\mu_{\text{eff}} = \langle g \rangle \sqrt{S(S+1)}$$

$$K = \frac{\langle A \rangle}{P} + \langle g \rangle - 2.0023$$

The magnetic moment values of the copper(II) chalcone complexes clearly indicate the absence of any antiferromagnetic coupling. The values further indicate that the complexes are mononuclear¹⁶ in these solvents.

TABLE 2—ESR, BONDING AND MAGNETIC PARAMETERS OF COPPER-CHALCONE COMPLEXES* IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS**

Parameter	1	2	3	4
$\langle g \rangle$	2.088 4 ^a	—	2.087 6	2.086 8
	2.104 2 ^b	—	2.102 2	2.108 8
	2.113 8 ^c	2.109 5	2.105 7	2.109 9
	2.116 4 ^d	2.119 8	2.118 1	2.115 5
$\langle A \rangle \times 10^4 (\text{cm}^{-1})$	50.51 ^a	—	49.51	49.01
	45.19 ^b	—	44.66	44.78
	41.94 ^c	41.86	44.04	42.85
	41.50 ^d	40.82	49.12	41.09
α^2	0.526 5 ^a	—	0.518 1	0.519 0
	0.528 8 ^b	—	0.520 7	0.524 2
	0.530 2 ^c	0.520 0	0.524 9	0.526 7
	0.535 5 ^d	0.535 8	0.547 9	0.528 6
K	0.226 4 ^a	—	0.222 8	0.220 6
	0.227 4 ^b	—	0.223 9	0.225 4
	0.228 0 ^c	0.223 5	0.225 7	0.226 6
	0.229 4 ^d	0.230 4	0.235 6	0.227 8
$\chi_M \times 10^4 \text{ CGS}$	1.364 ^a	—	1.363	1.362
	1.385 ^b	—	1.382	1.384
	1.397 ^c	1.392	1.387	1.392
	1.401 ^d	1.405	1.403	1.400
μ_{eff} (B.M.)	1.808 ^a	—	1.808	1.807
	1.822 ^b	—	1.821	1.822
	1.831 ^c	1.827	1.824	1.827
	1.833 ^d	1.845	1.834	1.832

* Compd. no. as in Table 1. **Solvents: ^achloroform, ^bdioxan, ^cDMF ^dpyridine.

complex, the smaller is the value of unpaired electron's wave function at the nucleus. Apparently, the bonding solvent pulls the electron away from the copper.

Bond nature and magnetic parameters: In a spectrum taken in solution the isotropic nuclear hyperfine splitting $\langle A \rangle$ is related to the covalency of the unpaired electron by the equation,

References

1. S. S. MISHRA and R. S. TRWARI, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1972, 35, 95.
2. S. S. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 68.
3. P. F. DEVITT, A. TIMONBY and M. A. VICKARS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 4941.
4. N. P. BUU-HOI and N. D. XUONG, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, 23, 39.
5. S. C. KUSHAWAHA, DINAKAR and J. B. LAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 82.
6. G. W. WILSON and D. E. FLOYD, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.*, 1949, 95, 399.
7. M. KAMODA, *J. Agric. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1954, 28, 791.
8. K. SYAMASUNDAR, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1964, 60, 259.
9. K. SYAMASUNDAR, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1968, 67, 90.
10. R. R. NAIDU, *Curr. Sci.*, 1968, 37, 342.
11. R. R. NAIDU, *Talanta*, 1975, 22, 615.
12. R. S. NAIDU and R. R. NAIDU, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1975, 82, 142.
13. R. S. NAIDU and R. R. NAIDU, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, 41, 1625.
14. R. L. BELFORD, M. CALVIN and G. BELFORD, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1957, 26, 1165.
15. C. KESAVULU, R. S. NAIDU and R. R. NAIDU, *Polyhedron*, 1985, 4, 761.
16. M. KATO, H. B. JONASSEN and J. C. FANNING, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, 99.